

BEUCITIZEN
BARRIERS TOWARDS EU CITIZENSHIP

Scenarios for EU citizenship in 2030

Repertoires for action in thinkable futures

Document Identifier

D11.5 - Report on 'EU citizenship 2030 - scenarios for future development'

Version

1.0

Date Due

28/02/2017 (M46)

Submission date

24/04/2017

WorkPackage

WP11

Lead Beneficiary

CEU

Dissemination Level

PU

Grant Agreement Number 320294
SSH.2012.1-1

Change log

Version	Date	amended by	changes
1.0	21.04.2017	Wieger Bakker	Submitted to coordination team

Partners involved

number	partner name	People involved
1	UU	Wieger Bakker Marlot van der Kolk

Table of contents

Table of contents.....	3
1. Introduction.....	5
2. EU citizenship today	7
3. Driving forces, trends and disruptive events.....	10
3.1 Four driving forces in a two continua model	10
3.2 Trends.....	11
3.3 Disruptive events.....	12
4. Imagining alternative futures: scenarios for EU citizenship in 2030.....	14
4.1 Future scenarios	14
4.2 A Europe of Parochial Solidarity – Scenario 1: more nationalism, more state	15
4.3 A Federal Fortress Europe – Scenario 2: more Europeanism, more state	16
4.4 A ‘Marketized’ Europe – scenario 3: more Europeanism, more market.....	17
4.5 A Europe of patchwork markets – scenario 4: more nationalism, more market.....	19
5. Values, assessment and repertoires of action	21
5.1 Values of EU citizenship.....	21
5.2 A Europe of Parochial Solidarity – Scenario 1: more nationalism, more state	22
5.3 A Federal Fortress Europe: scenario 2: more Europeanism, more state	23
5.4 A ‘Marketized’ Europe – scenario 3: more Europeanism, more market.....	24
5.5 A Europe of Patchwork Markets – scenario 4: more nationalism, more market.....	25
6. Conclusion	27
References.....	29

1. Introduction

European Union (EU) citizenship is both about a legal status - a set of civil, social, economic and political rights complementing one's national citizenship - and about being an active participating member of the EU political community. EU citizenship includes therefore influencing decisionmaking on rules, policies and practices that effect one's own national and local societies. The opportunities and capacities to exercise these rights and to participate differ between countries, between groups and in time. Social, cultural and economic trends, national or regional crises, as well as national and EU policy responses to these trends and crises, create potentially new inequalities, new barriers, but possibly new opportunities too. Although we cannot predict the future, we can prepare ourselves for different thinkable futures. Through this study we intend to feed the discussion on what might happen with EU citizenship in different circumstances. Moreover, by doing so we also want to stimulate the discussion on what repertoires of action by which actors in what circumstances might protect, foster or boost EU citizenship in these alternative futures.

With that in mind, we conducted a scenario study. A scenario is a story about how the future might unfold for organizations, issues, nations or even for the world. The scenario method is originated in the military sphere and was adapted and further developed by consulting firms and companies in the 1950s and 1960s. Pioneering work was conducted in the 1970s by the oil company Shell (Meinert, 2014, p.8). According to Shell (2008, pp.12-19), a scenario study should be carried out to (1) confront assumptions, (2) recognise degrees of uncertainty, (3) widen perspectives, and (4) address dilemmas and conflicts. Over the years, many companies as well as public organisations and governments confronted with the necessity of long-term investment or strategic decisions in a rapidly changing environment followed Shell's example and started to utilise scenarios for their strategy developments.

Building and using scenarios can help exploring what the future might look like and the likely implications of living in it. This stimulates the learning process and strengthens sensitivities in relation to possible future developments and changes (Shell, 2008, p.8). As Scarce and others formulate it "Scenario thinking is a tool for motivating people to challenge the status quo, or get better at doing so, by asking "What if?" Asking "What if?" in a disciplined way allows you to rehearse the possibilities of tomorrow, and then to take action today empowered by those provocations and insights" (Scarce et al. 2004, p.2). Although the focus is on the future, the scenario method stimulates the present decision-making process. As Gerald Davis (executive Chair of the World Energy Scenarios flagship study) mentioned: "*Scenarios are stories about the future, but their purpose is to make better decisions in the present*" (Wilkinson and Kupers, 2014).

Recently, the European Commission (2017) presented its 'White Paper on the Future of Europe'. In this White Paper, the Commission presents five thinkable future scenarios for Europe by 2025. The starting point of each of these scenarios is a different (policy) decision, and in the study is analysed what plausible consequences and impact each decisions might have on the future of the EU and its citizens. The main question is: what happens if we decide for one or another option. In this study, we use an opposite position. Here the main question is: when Europe develops in one or another direction, what options for choices do we have? For this we use known trends, events and driving forces in society as a starting point as well as the EU citizenship as we know it today, including the

values on which it is founded. Based on these trends, events and forces, we explore what futures we can imagine (plural) for 2030 and assess the consequences of these futures for EU citizenship.

Based on the outcomes of the bEUcitizen project and five scenario workshops, we developed four thinkable future scenarios for how the EU, or the part of Europe which now is the EU, might look like in 12 to 15 years (and beyond). These scenarios are not predictions, preferences or forecasts for the future. The scenarios represent plausible, relevant and challenging possibilities, and are a starting point for thinking about possible implications for EU citizenship as well as repertoires of action. In the workshops¹ more than sixty researchers, students and (young) professionals were engaged. Together we looked into how the future might unfold for EU citizenship: *how might the world look like in 2030 and what could this mean for EU citizenship? Is it likely that EU citizenship will change, will become broader, more specific, and more exclusive or not survive at all? Who will be more or less vulnerable? What in those different situations should and can be done by whom to safeguard EU citizenship or the values it stands for? What repertoire of action is needed and/or is possible in different circumstances and who is able to perform these actions?* In this report we present a synthesis of the insights gained from the scenario workshops as well as the outcomes of the bEUcitizen project.

Before we start sketching our thinkable futures, it is important to specify the concept of 'EU citizenship' and to summarize the characteristics of EU citizenship in today's world (Chapter 2). The environment within and around EU citizenship is dynamic and rapidly changing. Therefore, in Chapter 3, we describe influential trends and disruptive events that either are already visible or thinkable. The scenarios are outlined in Chapter 4. Here we identify critical driving forces that are seen as dominant for the coming years, but might develop in different directions, and we present our four thinkable scenarios. In Chapter 5, EU citizenship and the most important values for EU citizenship are assessed for each of the scenarios and we present some roughly sketches of possible repertoires of action that might fit those scenarios in protecting, fostering or boosting EU-citizenship. In our conclusion we summarize the main findings of this modest scenario study.

Before we take off, one disclaimer has to be made. This study is not reflecting the personal preferences of the authors nor the preferences of the participants of the scenario workshops. We do not state by this study that EU-citizenship has to develop or has to be stimulated in one way or another. What we try to do is to analyse first, what might happen with EU citizenship in different circumstances? And second, if one strives for protecting, fostering or boosting EU-citizenship, what choices can be made, what options for action are available to do so, given these different circumstances.

¹ The workshops were held in Zagreb (June 29 2015 Croatia), Oviedo (June 30 2016 Spain), and three were held in Utrecht (May 19 2016, February , March 10 2017, April 12 2017 the Netherlands).

2. EU citizenship today

For a rough sketch of the characteristics of EU citizenship as we know it today, we use the well-known distinction between the liberal and the republican model of citizenship. These two models stand for two dimensions of citizenship that are related in what we call EU citizenship. The liberal model refers to citizenship as a legal status. It contains the specific set of political, economic, civil and social rights each citizen of an EU Member State has *in addition* to his or her national citizenship rights. The republican model of citizenship, the communitarian aspect included, is about the identification with and active membership of a European political community. Here, citizenship is understood as an active social practice of ‘belonging’ (Leydet, 2011; Marshall, 1950; Kymlicka and Norman, 1995; Dell’Olio, 2005).

In this scenario study we look not only at both dimensions of EU citizenship, but keep in mind the values or principles EU citizenship is based upon as well. When asked, our workshop participants defined these values and principles almost unanimously in the same words as the words used to describe the founding principles of the EU; ‘human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities’. Summarized, EU citizenship stands for them for:

1. Democracy and (political) participation;
2. European unity in diversity;
3. Peace and stability;
4. Inclusiveness and solidarity;
5. Protection and human security.

When analysing what might happen with EU citizenship given different imagined futures and exploring what can be done to foster citizenship, we not only look at the existing and formalized EU citizenship rights, but also at the implications for realizing these principles within the Europe of the EU.

The way EU citizenship as a legal status looks like can be summarized as follows.² Apart from the, since 2009, legally binding EU charter on fundamental rights, one can distinguish the following categories of rights. *Civil rights* provide personal liberties as well as equality before the law and structure the relationship between citizens. In the case of EU citizenship this includes for example respect for the integrity of persons (Art. 3 CFREU), the right to marry and found a family (Art. 9 CFREU) and the equality before the law (Art. 20. CFREU). *Political rights* guarantee citizens participation in exercising legitimate power and protects citizens against abuse of power by their governments. EU citizenship grants EU citizens that live in another EU country the right to vote in municipal elections (Art. 40 CFREU), the right to petition (Art. 44 CFREU) and the right to a fair trial (Art. 47 CFREU). *Social rights*, require states to guarantee minimal living conditions. With regard to EU citizenship, examples are the right to education (Art. 14 CFREU), the right to social security (Art. 34 CFREU) and the right to health care (Art. 35 CFREU). *Economic rights* one has as a EU citizen refer to the right to exchange goods, services, capital (not in charter) and the freedom to conduct a business (Art. 16. CFREU). Furthermore, economic rights protect citizens against market deficits (e.g. Information asymmetry or monopolies) by granting them several consumer rights (Art. 38 CFREU).

² This section is based on Bakker and De Krijger 2016, D 11.1, p. 16/17

European Union Citizenship			
Civil rights	Political rights	Social rights	Economic rights
Free movement of persons and residence	Representative European and local elections	Right to health care	Free movement of goods, services and capital.
Equal treatment of EU citizen.	Direct political participation	Right to education	Consumer protection
Cross-border divorces and separations	Respect of Crime victims' rights and a fair trial	Right to social security	
	Accountable European governance		

Active membership of a European –political- community refers to different activities of citizens that express involvement in the development and functioning of the Union and active engagement in realizing their rights. From voting and standing for local or regional elections to bringing ideas to the EU by taking part in a citizens initiative. And from cross-border activities as student exchange or moving to another country for work, to being active in the European public sphere (EC, 2012, p.40 and 53; EC, 2013, 34-40).

When the Treaty of Maastricht (1992) introduced EU citizenship, these two dimensions, ‘rights’ and ‘active membership’ were considered to be related. The assumption was that granting national citizens of the member states, the legal status of EU citizen would result in a feeling of belonging to a shared European community and identity, and would result in active political participation as well. The assumption was that there was a causal relation between the two dimensions (Bakker et al., 2016, p.8). In 2007, the Lisbon Treaty strengthened EU citizenship by making the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights legally binding and by expanding the opportunities for democratic participation and increasing the visibility of EU citizen rights. However, it is observed that there are still many obstacles in the way of citizens exercising their rights (European Commission, 2010; 2013) and in the development of a European identity. Empirical evidence suggest that, in the EU context, there is no causal relationship between the launching of EU citizenship and the development of a European identity (Dell’Olio, 2005).

Outcomes of the research done within the bEUcitizen project support these suggestions. Due to several factors, barriers towards EU citizenship exist and the chances and opportunities to exercise rights and to participate in the wider –political- community differ between countries, between groups and in time. The following three factors are clearly visible in the outcomes of the bEUcitizen research projects (Bakker and Van der Kolk, 2016). First there is a so-called ‘link approach’ or a ‘marketization’ of citizenship visible in Member States. This refers to the situation where a persons’ access to rights is linked with / depends on meeting specific conditions and/or requirements, such as registration requirements, residency requirements, the labour market position or the market status of the individuals. Citizenship is linked to conditions and/or requirements which are shaped by (national) governments and create inequalities in access to and the exercise of EU citizenship between and within Member States (for examples see: Seeleib-Kaiser and Chase, 2015; Pennings et al., 2016; Luppi et al., 2015; Anderson et al., 2016). Bureaucracy is a second factor that can lead to a barrier for citizens to exercise their EU citizenship effectively. For example, administrative burdens

with regard to accessing travel documents, can be a barrier, especially in the case of applications to the benefit of minors that are foreign-born (De Waele, 2016). Thirdly, differences between legal systems of Member States can create obstacles. An EU citizen has certain core rights based on EU law, because of the fact he/she is an EU citizen, but for the substance of that right he/she is mostly dependent on the national laws of the Member State in which he/she resides (Van Eijken and Phoa, 2016; De Waele, 2016).

The outcomes of the bEUcitizen project show that there are vulnerable (southern and eastern) countries, regions and, in particular, vulnerable groups. Specific groups are identified as vulnerable in their access to and in exercising EU citizenship. For instance, the low voter turnout in European elections is related to social inequality of voting. Socially weak EU citizens are overrepresented in the group of non-voters. This group is outside the political system and its members do not exercise their political rights (Gaus and Seubert, 2016). Also, there is an evident move towards a knowledge-based economy and attracting the 'brightest and the best' across the EU. This results in restricted access for lower skilled workers (Anderson et al., 2014). Summarizing the finding in a too general categorization, one can argue that a weak unstable socio-economic position makes one vulnerable in getting access to and exercising EU citizenship and that different factors can contribute to that, such as being mobile, moving and migrating or certain personal characteristics such as age, gender or being member of a specific minority. Within the bEUcitizen project the following vulnerable groups were identified and studied in more detail:

- Socially weak citizens (Seubert, 2016)
- Low skilled workers (Anderson et al., 2014)
- Economically inactive EU citizens (Van Eijken and Phoa, 2016; Pennings et al., 2016);
- EU migrant citizens (Seeleib-Kaiser and Chase, 2015);
- Mobile EU citizens (De Waele, 2016);
- Asylum seekers (Anderson et al., 2015; Anderson et al., 2016)
- Women, and in particular migrant women (Knijn et al., 2014; Rolandsen Agustin and Nissen, 2015);
- Youth (Knijn et al., 2014);
- Elderly (Knijn et al., 2014);
- Roma (Anderson et al., 2014).

In sum, EU citizenship today has multi-dimensional characteristics and interacts in a multi-level environment. Barriers towards EU citizenship exist and the chances and opportunities to exercise rights and community participation differ between countries, between groups and in time. Besides, the environment within and around EU citizenship is dynamic and rapidly changing. Therefore, in the next section, influential trends and disruptive events in the current situation are described.

3. Driving forces, trends and disruptive events

Looking at what factors and forces will or may shape the future of Europe, the EU or, more specific, EU citizenship, we look at what driving forces are relevant, what trends can be taken into account and what kind of disruptive events might directly or indirectly affect conditions for (EU) citizenship. The selection below comes from the outcomes of bEUcitizen research, the earlier mentioned series of five workshops and more general literature and policy documents on the development of the EU. Together, specific configurations of these factors will be used in the following chapter to sketch four imaginable futures for EU citizenship that clearly discriminate from one another³.

3.1 Four driving forces in a two continua model

We identified four driving forces that according to the participants of the aforementioned scenario workshops, are the most relevant because they are for a longer period visible throughout Europe, can be regarded 'critical' in terms of the impact they might have on EU citizenship and can be seen as the ends of two continua. The first continuum is about, at the same time, the level of identification, integration and governance in Europe. Here we see at the one hand growing nationalism throughout Europe as a strong driving force. Partly due to the refugee, debt, and terrorist crises, existing and growing social cleavages within and between Member States, feelings of nationalism are strengthened, nationalist politics is becoming more important and policies protecting national interests are more and more advocated. But an opposite development is visible too. Europeanism is more explicitly expressed by part of the electoral parties and the electorate and the same crisis mentioned above, lead to (some) more cooperation and joint policy efforts on the level of the EU. One can imagine one of both becoming dominant over the other in the future.

The second continuum deals with the primacy in regulating society: state or market. On the one hand we come from decades in which the role of the market in creating the greatest wealth and wellbeing for all was seen as dominant, including the privatisation of public services. The role of the EU for a larger part was looked upon as facilitating and supporting the well functioning of the single market. At the other hand, and partly again in reaction to different sorts of crisis, the state is to a certain extent brought back. Member states, governments, regained power to control and protect the wellbeing of their citizens in response to, for instance, the financial crisis and the refugee crisis. Here too one can imagine in which in the future there will be a dominance of the state over the market or vice versa.

These are critical and at the same time uncertain forces, that will shape the future. The dimensions involve (extreme) opposites, which might lead to different future worlds. Therefore, based on all thinkable future outcomes, four scenarios are developed.

Figure 1: Driving forces.

³ We are aware that the description of these forces, trends and events is limited. However, for this scenario study it is not needed to examine these more in detail. They are mentioned briefly to give the reader an idea and overview of forces, trends and events that influenced the scenarios.

3.2 Trends

In discussing overarching, international, trends that are likely to influence the scope of citizenship as well as opportunities in exercising citizenship five more sustainable trends were mentioned that have to be taken into account.

First of all there is the *geopolitical change of eroding Western domination* on the (economic) world stage. The economic power of other regions is rising. Asia already is more in the centre of the world economy. Also, there are tensions between Western and Eastern countries (for instance, European Union and Russia) and tensions within the Middle East (Van der Putten, Rood and Meijnders, 2016).

Secondly there is a *reverse trend with lesser space for cultural diversity*. The dominant trend was a long time from a primarily national and cultural homogeneous pattern to a more globalised culture with extensive room for diversity. This is changing since the last 10 to 20 years into two more and more antagonistic developments: one still oriented towards globalisation and diversity and the other towards a national orientation with a focus re-establishing a homogeneous in-group identity. There is a tendency to create and stimulate cohesive, unified communities of citizens (Conversi, 2010). However, cohesive communities provoke differential biases toward in-groups and out-groups. In-groups are the groups to which individuals belong and psychologically identify, while out-groups do not belong and/or identify themselves with the community. This has an impact on social interactions, including group conflicts, stereotyping and prejudice (Nelson, 2009) within the local, the national and the EU community.

Thirdly, one can observe a *reevaluation of authoritarian leadership*. After World War II, states and citizens emphasized prevention from authoritarian leadership through various institutional checks and balances in democratic political institution and through forms of civic education. Nowadays there is more room for and appreciation of authoritarian leadership as well as for the use of specific and direct powers and jurisdiction of (political) leaders inside and outside the EU. An example is the use of declaring the state of emergency in for instance France and Turkey. Also, media and civil society seem to become the target of a crackdown from governments in countries as Hungary and Poland. Furthermore, citizens' acceptance of EU institutions and decisions seems to be eroding, notable in for instance Brexit and the raising national parties in countries as France, the Netherlands and Poland.

Fourthly, there is *increasing access to the Internet, social media and technology*. Citizens are continuously and in real time connected all over the world. Technology is developing rapidly and is becoming more extreme. For instance, progress in robotics or artificial intelligence are becoming more evident. These technological developments have huge implications for industries, such as transport and logistics, health care and customer service (Pew Research Center, 2014). But also the – political- participation of citizens in the public sphere is in transformation.

The fifth and last trend mentioned is that of Earth's *changing climate*. The climate change is visible in, for instance, the rising sea level, rising global temperature, the warming of oceans and the declining of Arctic sea ice. Impacts for nature, the economy and health differ across regions, territories and economic sectors in Europe (NASA, 2016). Climate change raises questions over ecological citizenship and environmental migration.

3.3 Disruptive events

Where driving forces and trends have a certain element of predictability, disruptive events may turn out to become what are called 'game changers'. Over the years we have witnessed the effects of such game changers in Europe on several occasions: from the collapse of the Soviet Union at the end of the nineties to the effects of 9/11 and from the financial crisis of 2008 to the unanticipated migration flows of 2016. Although we will not include too specific imaginable game changers in our short scenarios on EU citizenship, it is sensible to be aware of what 'usual' types of game changers can be distinguished and to be aware that they can interact with existing trends, can disturb an existing equilibrium or can fuel dramatically an already present development.

For instance, we are already witnessing how *terrorist acts and war* elsewhere can to a certain extent become indigenous for the EU countries; leading to a decrease of social cohesion, extensive security measures interfering with existing privacy rights and, at the same time, lead to new migration flows. On a global scale, the number of terrorist incidents has been increasing for the last ten years (Institute for Economics and Peace, 2015). There have been various terrorist attacks in the European Union, for instance in Brussels, Paris, Nice, Berlin and Copenhagen. As a result, lines between internal and external threats are blurred and is changing the way people think about personal safety and borders (European Commission, 2017, p.11). Also, European citizens continue to be kidnapped and killed in conflict zones abroad. This have been exacerbated due the conflicts in Syria, Afghanistan and Iraq and the rising threat of ISIS. Another concern for Member States are EU citizens and residents travelling to conflict zones to fight alongside extremist groups (Archick et al., 2015).

The recent migration flows come from different parts of the world (European Commission, 2017). The last year, migration was increasing and increasingly more refugees came to Europe, fleeing Middle Eastern conflicts (European Youth Press, 2016). Europe is facing the largest refugee crisis since World War II; Europe saw 1.2 million people coming in 2015 (European Commission, 2017). As a result, the European Member States are facing rising Asylum applicants (European Parliament, 2016).

Another example of a recent disruptive event is the *economic crisis* that kick started in 2007-08 and resulted in the biggest recession (2008-09) since the Great Depression of the 1930s. The impact of the crisis has been deep on society and increased the imbalances within the European Union (Terazi and Şenel, 2011). The EU economy is now back on a more stable footing. However, the recovery is still unevenly distributed across society and regions. This is particularly relevant for the younger generation. For the first time since World War II, there is a risk that the generation of today's young adults ends up less well-off than their parents (European Commission, 2017). Also, in the last decade, structural unemployment in Southern and Eastern Europe as well as income inequalities have led to an increase in mobility from poorer EU countries to regions which have a stronger economy (Granger, 2016).

Apart from these disruptive events one can imagine that large scale natural disasters (drought in Africa), pandemic outbreaks or industrial disasters (nuclear incident) also might lead to effects that

influence EU citizenship. In our scenario's we do not take one specific disruptive event as a starting point, but imagine that some might have happened, leading to, for instance new migration flows of more rigorous safety measures.

4. Imagining alternative futures: scenarios for EU citizenship in 2030

4.1 Future scenarios

By combining the critical driving forces of the two continua, we can construct a set of four different future scenarios. In the following paragraphs we present these four thinkable but imagined futures (see Figure 2):

1. *A Europe of Parochial Solidarity*: in which the nationalism, state intervention and state guaranteed social security are dominant;
2. *A Federal Fortress Europe*: where supra-national state intervention is combined with Europeanism, protecting those with EU citizenship within the EU, protecting the EU from outsiders;
3. *A Marketized Europe*: in which the market power by market actors is dominant and goes side by side with Europeanism;
4. *A Europe of patchwork markets*: where the interests of nations and national and regional markets are dominant and the variation of the characteristics and powers between these markets is high.

These scenarios are not predictions, preferences or forecasts for the future. The scenarios represent to a certain extent plausible, relevant and challenging futures, and are a starting point for both assessing implications for EU citizenship and discussing repertoires of action to foster citizenship. The four future scenarios are described in the narrative of how the EU, Europe, might look in 2030. The year 2030 is chosen for these four future worlds as it enables creative thinking: it is distant enough from the present to allow substantial shifts, and at the same time it is close enough to present day discussions to be plausible. There are overlaps between the scenarios and they are therefore neither mutually exclusive, nor exhaustive.

Figure 2: Thinkable future scenarios.

4.2 A Europe of Parochial Solidarity – Scenario 1: more nationalism, more state

What happened?

Due the refugee, financial, and terrorist crises and along the line of already existing social cleavages within Member States and between Member States, the legitimacy of the EU and the pro-EU national political parties became more and more contested. There was a significant diminution of the legitimacy of the EU and the citizens' acceptance of European institutions further eroded (Cheneval, 2016). "Brussels" continuously had to take the blame for failing cooperation between member states while national politicians were taking credit for successes at home (European Commission, 2017). Especially the perceived threat of costs associated with EU migrant citizens contributed to a growing mistrust towards the EU. Some member states followed the British example (Brexit) or renegotiated opt out positions, and retrenched social rights for EU migrant citizens (Seeleib-Kaiser, 2017).

Moreover, the decrease in voter turnouts for the European Parliament continued. In countries with a relative high voter turnout, the Eurosceptic parties received more support. Privileged, high educated citizens were and are (political) more active compared to lower educated parts of the population due to their opinion that being active will not make any difference. A growing number of politically active citizens follow populist and Eurosceptic parties as they consider European solidarity to be too expensive and expect national policies to be more effective too in safeguarding their privileges (Eberl and Seubert, 2016). These tendencies contributed to a disintegration of the EU and, resulted in a Europe of parochial solidarity where the EU member states continued to organise solidarity on the level of the nation state and in line with existing traditions.

By 2030.....

Citizens of –former- EU countries returned largely to the nation state as locus of legitimate democratic self-government, while national governments are forced to favour what is perceived as the national interest (Cheneval, 2016). National governments do not accept interference of the EU in policy areas that are traditionally seen as the domain of the nation state; security, immigration, defence, asylum policy, education and social security. Consequently, the EU is primarily facilitating trade and trade relations.

The Member states prime focus is on the centralisation of power on the level of the nation state. The process of transferring sovereignty from the national to the supra national level is turned around and the member states took back control: from safeguarding borders to protecting the well-being of their citizens. More states define the requirements and conditions in terms of citizens' contribution to society on which a persons' access to social rights depends, in particular for non-national citizens. High taxes make it possible to provide provisions in those countries that where that is possible.

The differences between member states increased in terms of economic prosperity and in terms of social rights. Competition between member states increased as well. Some countries are able to recruit the work force they need from other member states and granting these workers some kind of citizenship rights, leading in some cases to a brain drain in the countries from origin.

The EU, especially the Commission and the Parliament, is increasingly less powerful and more passive. Overarching interests hardly are formulated as common interests. This complicated the

collective decision-making on the level of the EU and blocked policy making and political decision making on that level. To bring European politics closer to the national arenas and to the locus of national democracy, a treaty change has taken place to inscribe the rights of national parliaments to repel secondary EU legislation by simple majority. Hence, national parliaments can review EU (trade) decisions. A significant number of national parliaments have the possibility to block a law decision that has been taken at the EU level (Cheneval, 2016).

Characteristics of a Europe of parochial solidarity:

- Member states took power;

- Member states provide the provisions for a decent life;

- The EU is primarily about trade relations;

- National parliaments review EU decisions.

4.3 A Federal Fortress Europe – Scenario 2: more Europeanism, more state

What happened?

National pro-EU political parties have become significantly more popular across Europe as they, as well as a majority of the electorate, experienced that individual member states and national institutions are not equipped to deal with the most important challenges: from financial crisis to climate crisis to refugee- and terrorist crises. Following further international turmoil due to war and draughts in Africa and parts of Asia, the member states decided to share more power, resources and decision-making on the EU level (European Commission, 2017). As a result, the EU Member States managed to cooperate in such a way that they were able to control the refugee, debt, and terrorist crises.

The EU strengthened its role on the global level and even some non EU countries like the UK, Norway and Switzerland, cooperated in a joint effort to address common challenges. Especially with a series of international treaties the relations with some North-African countries (Morocco, Tunisia, Libya) and Turkey were renewed and intensified with respect to these issues. Through the visible effectiveness of the protection of the EU borders and the sending back significant numbers of asylum seekers, more citizens were mobilized for the political participation on the level of the EU and through the debates on these common issues, even a mature European Public Sphere developed. The voter turnout for the European Parliament increased, with a strong participation of both the lower classes and the cosmopolitan elites (Eberl and Seubert, 2016). The political will for further integration continued, leading to a cooperation far beyond previous periods in a broader spectrum of policy areas (European Commission, 2017). These developments led gradually to for more support for a Federal Europe, where the EU acts as a single sovereign federation of states on those domains that are crucial for the economic development, social inclusion, sustainable future, border security and the integrity of the Union.

By 2030.....

The EU intervenes in a large number of policy areas, such as security, immigration, defence and asylum policy. Defence and security are the main priority of the EU; a European Defence Union is created and the EU continues the fight against climate change (European Commission, 2017). The EU

is active in policy areas that traditionally belonged to the exclusive competence of member states, such as education and social security. The EU plays a key role in the protection and promotion of the social and economic well-being of citizens. It provides the minimal provisions for a decent life for those who are unable to avail themselves. This has led to the development of minimum social rights within the EU, including the introduction of a European Minimum Income Scheme (Seeleib-Kaiser, 2017). There is also more coordination on fiscal, social and taxation matters and European supervision of financial services intensified (European Commission, 2017). Fiscal integration makes it possible to finance the EU budget by own resources.

The EU completed the single market in the fields of energy, new technologies and services. On the international scene, Europe speaks and acts as one in trade agreements and is represented by one seat in most international fora. The EU as an integrated capital market, helps to mobilise finance for enterprises and major infrastructure projects across the EU (European Commission, 2017). The Euro is the only currency within the EU. The EU supports the promotion of EU citizenship by further opening the borders within the EU and by promoting and supporting mobility.

Democratic decision making moved for a larger part to the federal level. The EU becomes a full parliamentary democracy, where the parliament legislates on all common matters and can express a political majority and a government following the European elections. The parliament is accountable to the European Parliament and to a reformed Council transformed in a second legislative chamber or senate. The new EU federal government and its composition reflect the result of the European elections. It has the final say on international trade agreements, EU financing, the governance of the Euro and foreign and security policy. The member states keep their autonomy in matters of public services, education and culture.

Characteristics of a Federal Europe:

- The EU has a European federal government, active in a broad spectrum of policy areas;
- EU guarantees minimal provisions for a decent life;
- EU coordination on fiscal, social and taxation matters as well as an integrated capital market;
- EU invests extensively in federal border protection and defence;
- EU government responsible for foreign affairs, defence and immigration.

4.4 A 'Marketized' Europe – scenario 3: more Europeanism, more market

What happened?

Since the economic- and especially the refugee crises, the support for more state intervention evaporated. Dissatisfaction with mainstream politics and institutions on all levels rocketed sky high everywhere in the EU. This manifested itself through a constant mistrust towards actions of public authorities. Member states took no ownership for joint-decisions and politicians were finger-pointing at each other on the national and EU level. As a result, citizens' trust in the EU decreased parallel to a decrease in trust in national authorities (European Commission, 2017).

These developments stimulated a high degree and an almost exponential process of deregulation, which led to a transfer of power from states and public authorities to market actors. Multinationals as Google, Shell and Coca Cola are in the centre and more or less rule societies, or at least the labour

markets and the work conditions on it. The main and almost sole focus of the EU is the functioning of and to complete the single market. Especially the internationally active businesses, corporations and other market actors stimulated this EU focus on the free market, including trade and efficiency and facilitating industries in further technological development and innovation. Corporations have been investing in robotics and artificial intelligence to automating away many substitutable jobs. The new digital technologies contribute to the improvement of efficiency and to globalization as well as to the linguistic unification within the EU. These developments have led to what can be called a marketized Europe.

By 2030.....

The EU is primarily active in a facilitating and supervising the functioning of the single market and in facilitating and stimulating economic growth and economic innovation. At the same time the EU has become less political and has become less visible in other domains. In a way, the EU functions internally as a supra national chamber of commerce. Within the EU there is consensus on the approach to international trade, which makes it possible for the EU to conclude deals with partners outside the EU (European Commission, 2017). In its relation to the member states the EU is active in preventing national regulation that hinders the single market or constitutes barriers for exercising the freedom of movement of persons, goods, capital and services.

In many policy domains, including public services, the market and market actors are dominant and active on the level of the EU and beyond. Not only in insurance, but also in education, health care, security and policing. The level of these services is partly dependent on national or regional differences in purchasing power and partly dependent on internationally agreed quality standards and benchmarks. As a result social differences persist and deepen between EU countries and regions. Social inequality is growing fast and leading to new divides also in areas, such as the environment, that are not directly covered due to a vacuum between market actors, relatively weak national governments and the EU (European Commission, 2017).

As a result of the investments in the progress of robotics and artificial intelligence, many substitutable jobs are automated away. Companies retrained staff to master technological developments, and had to let go many other employees. The employees who had to leave are stimulated to look for jobs in other sectors and in other places, including other countries. Access to social rights but also the freedom of movement and residence, strongly depends on the contribution to the economic welfare of the EU. Overall there a significant re-commodification of labour. Access to rights is not available for all EU citizens. The focus is on attracting the 'brightest and the best' across the EU to stimulate the knowledge-based economy (Anderson et al., 2014). For citizens from outside the EU, an annual membership fee is asked. In this way, third national citizens can buy their EU citizenship. Citizens organize themselves less around political parties and more around their position in the economy, either as workers or as clients and consumers.

Characteristics of a marketized Europe:

- The EU is primarily active in domains related to the functioning of the single market;
- There is a strong focus on deregulation;
- Cooperation on common concerns depends on the capacity of governments and companies;
- Social inequality is growing, rights are conditional and related to positions on the labour market;

- Organising around economic interests becomes more important than traditional democratic processes on the national and the EU level;
-
- Access to (EU) rights can be bought by third national citizens.

4.5 A Europe of patchwork markets – scenario 4: more nationalism, more market

What happened?

Partly due to the economic- and refugee crises, but also due to asymmetrical benefits from the internal market in some sectors, there has been a growing decline in support for the EU, in decrease of trust in the capacities of national governments to protect its citizens from the Europeanisation of the economy and steep rising call for protecting national economies and labour markets. “Brussels” has been blamed for negative, specific and local, effects of the internal market while national politicians were blamed for not protecting their national industries and labour force. This manifested itself through mistrust towards actions of public authorities (European Commission, 2017). The growing support for more nationalist policies and politics accelerated after it turned out that Brexit was more successful for the UK than expected. After some hesitation, other countries followed the British example (Denmark and Hungary) or decided to limit their cooperation as much as possible to trade-agreements (the Netherlands, Austria, France).

These tendencies have led to a strong but diverse deregulation on the national levels and profit driven societies, comparable to the ‘America first’ policy of the United States of America. The focus is on the nation and its market, but international trade and competition do play an important role to improve the market position of the nation. These tendencies have led in the direction of a patchwork Europe with a huge diversity of economies with their own characteristics, strengths and weaknesses that more and more diverge. Also these developments did lead to a growing amalgam of multi-lateral and bi-lateral agreements of different signatures.

By 2030

Many national governments are weak. The EU itself is on the edge of ceasing to exist altogether. There is no shared mission, no shared future for the Union. Given the strong focus on deregulation at the European and at the national level, differences persist and are increasing in areas such as consumer standards, social standards and environmental standards, as well as in taxation (European Commission, 2017). Countries are struggling to agree on rules on, for instance, the mobility of workers. Some countries managed to agree in multi-lateral and bi-lateral agreements, but there are no common rules and standards within Europe. Consequently, social inequality is growing fast, leading to new divides in and between countries. The competition between national markets is enormous and at the same time, markets that are losing the battle, become inner directed or try to survive as low income markets by attracting industries from markets that do well. Consequently, the EU as a whole is no longer represented in a number of international (trade) fora. Tensions between countries rise as inequalities in welfare deepen.

The picture of the whole of the former EU is mixed. Citizens are for a large part seen as employees and consumers. Their access to rights strongly depend on the contribution to the economic welfare. Access to rights is related to meeting certain requirements and/or conditions. What these rights are differ extensively from country to country. But at the same time there are new alliances between

market actors, national governments and interest organisations on the national level. Alliances that seek to protect both the national market as well as the position of the labour forces and its future.

Characteristics of a Europe as patchwork markets:

- Governments are weak, the EU ceases to exist;
- Inequalities in income within and between countries grow;
- The focus is on the nation and its market with a strong focus on deregulation;
- There is an increasing divergence in how countries, economies and markets develop ;
- There are no common rules and standards within Europe.

5. Values, assessment and repertoires of action

The scenarios presented in the previous chapter offer different images of the future. These images hopefully encourage people to discuss about what the implications of these futures are for EU citizenship. In this section we present some thoughts to kick-off this discussion by assessing first how likely it is that the values behind EU citizenship are safe in the sketched scenarios. Secondly we look for each scenario what might happen with (EU) citizenship and what can be done in that scenario to protect, foster or boost (EU) citizenship.

5.1 Values of EU citizenship

The Treaty of Maastricht (1992) introduced EU citizenship, and in 2007 the Lisbon Treaty strengthened EU citizenship by making the EU Charter of Fundamental rights legally binding and by expanding the opportunities for democratic participation and increasing the visibility of EU citizen rights. This reflects the importance of EU citizenship for the EU. As outlined in chapter 2, the participants of the workshops identified a set of values or principles that are regarded as important for EU citizenship and for a larger part mimic the founding principles of the EU. These principles are summarised in five key values for EU citizenship:

1. Democracy and (political) participation;
2. European unity in diversity;
3. Peace and stability;
4. Inclusiveness and solidarity;
5. Protection and human security.

Table 1 shows the implications for the values of EU citizenship in each of the scenarios.

<i>Values of EU citizenship</i>	Scenario 1: A Europe of parochial solidarity	Scenario 2: A Federal Fortress Europe	Scenario 3: A marketized Europe	Scenario 4: A Europe of patchwork markets
<i>Democracy and (political) participation</i>	Yes, especially on the national level, privileged citizens most active	Yes, minority positions under threat	Questionable	Questionable If so, on the national level
<i>European unity in diversity</i>	To some extent	Yes for unity, diversity questionable	To some extent	No
<i>Peace and stability</i>	Probable	Yes, within the EU	Unstable	Serious risks
<i>Inclusiveness and solidarity</i>	Yes, on the national level	Yes	To some extent	No, but variable on the national level
<i>Protection and human security</i>	Yes, on the national level	Yes	Minimal, related to labour market position	Minimal, on the national level

Table 1: Values of EU citizenship in each scenario.

5.2 A Europe of Parochial Solidarity – Scenario 1: more nationalism, more state

What will happen with EU citizenship?

In this scenario power is concentrated on the level of the nation state. Cooperation within the EU is limited to trade relations. Only some economic EU citizenship rights, such as the freedom of goods and capital, still exist, but other (social, political and civil) EU rights that complement ones national citizenship, do not exist anymore as such. The question is to what extent these national citizenship rights are accessible, in particular for non-national citizens. As more and more countries implemented restrictions, the access to rights is undermined for vulnerable groups as EU migrant citizens (Seeleib-Kaiser and Chase, 2015; Seeleib-Kaiser, 2017), mobile EU citizens (De Waele, 2016) and asylum seekers (Anderson et al., 2015; 2016).

Although the voter turnouts for the EP decreased, it is possible that democracy and democratic or political participation increase. In this scenario, national parliaments can block decisions taken at the EU level. This brings European politics closer to the national arena and to the locus of national democracy. However, it does not improve the legitimacy of decisions in the context of a general disenchantment with representative democracy and in contexts where national parliaments lack citizens acceptance (Cheneval, 2016). Besides, only privileged citizens are political active and underprivileged citizens remain passive. This raises the chance that socially weak EU citizens are still overrepresented in the group of non-voters and are not exercising their political rights (Eberl and Seubert, 2016; Gaus and Seubert, 2016).

In this scenario ‘European unity in diversity’ seems to be of lesser importance. There is unity with regard to trade relations and diversity with regard to national interests. In this way, national identities, cultures and traditions all exist without any relation to a European identity on an aggregate level. Borders are strong, freedom of movement restricted, right to asylum and the access (for some groups) to social rights limited. In this sense, diversity as an asset for the EU as a whole is marginal in a ‘Europe of parochial solidarity’.

In this scenario ‘peace and stability’ is to a certain extent met. Member states share an interest in peace and stability within the EU as unstable relations between the member states will affect trade relations. However, national governments will prioritize the protection of their own citizens. Non-nationals run the risk of becoming outsiders. ‘Inclusiveness and solidarity’ is less relevant on the level of the EU and on the level of the nation state especially for the (indigenous) insiders and less for movers and migrants.

In sum, EU citizenship will be significantly limited and restricted in a ‘Europe of parochial solidarity’. Some economic rights related to EU citizenship, such as the freedom of movement of goods and capital, might still exist. On the national level citizenship will be more limited to insiders. In some cases, strong nationalism and strong state intervention will pave the way for autocracies, in which national citizenship will decrease even further.

Repertoire of action

In this scenario, national governments and self-organizations of citizens, civil society, can play important roles to foster EU citizenship and to express the importance of the values behind it. National governments are strong enough to have the opportunity and resources to protect citizens and safeguard EU citizenship by, for instance, strengthening national law and legislation and to improve the access to rights for all citizens. Also, national parliaments have the power to block

decisions taken at the EU level but also vice versa. Secondly, through the involvement of national parliaments, EU institutions and decisions can create a more solid basis for citizens' acceptance of the European level. Therefore, the EU's potential to shape important decisions that could provide new legitimacy-enhancing democratic devices will be needed (Cheneval, 2016). Thirdly, civil society can play a role by fostering innovations. *"Civil society has the ability to experiment, move faster than government and act as an agent of change"* (World Economic Forum, 2013, p.14). This gives civil society actors an important role in this scenario.

5.3 A Federal Fortress Europe: scenario 2: more Europeanism, more state

What will happen with EU citizenship?

In a Federal Europe, the EU government interferes in all cross border policy areas and guarantees provisions for a decent life for those who are unable to sustain themselves. The EU plays a key role in the protection and promotion of the social and economic well-being of citizens, for instance by stimulating economic rights as the freedom of movement and by providing minimal social rights including the introduction of a European Minimum Income Scheme (Seeleib-Kaiser, 2017).

Although these developments boost in a way EU citizenship, there are questions too. First of all, some citizens may think that the EU took too much power away from the member states. Secondly, defining minimal social rights within the EU can raise questions about 'standards'. Will there be a race to the bottom, will certain rights or provisions be adjusted to average incomes for some citizens and countries? Thirdly, a strong focus on the European dimension can jeopardise national identities, cultures and traditions. Fourthly, extensive political integration will raise issues about the dominance of some countries (France, Germany) or regions (north-west EU). To what extent can the smaller EU Member States raise their voice? Lastly, the strong focus on the EU on securitisation of external borders and controlled immigration makes the access to the EU limited for third country nationals and puts pressure on asylum seekers and the existing migrant population.

Despite these uncertainties the values behind EU citizenship are most likely to be realised in this scenario. EU citizens are mobilized and voter turnouts for the EP may increase, with a fair chance of a strong participation of the lower classes as well as of the privileged, high educated cosmopolite elites (Eberl and Seubert, 2016). 'Democracy and political participation' are highly valued in this scenario as well as 'European unity in diversity'. A federal Europe is a strong unity. However, as a result of the promotion of a strong European identity, the cultural diversity that is promoted as an asset is at the same time under pressure. National identities run the risk of becoming extinct with younger generations which might lead to a counter movement.

Altogether this scenario leads to a high level of 'inclusiveness and solidarity' as well as to 'protection and human security' within the EU. However, this may also cause turmoil within the member states due to the high level of taxes that citizens pay for it, especially under those who are more privileged and have the feeling that they pay for others' wealth. This may also affect the high level of 'peace and stability' that exist within the EU to some extent, but it is not likely that high taxes will endanger peace. The more obvious peace is, the more likely it is that the public support for the EU level decreases.

Repertoire of action

In this scenario, the federal state is the prime guardian of EU citizenship. As long as the EU is able to show the necessity of concerted action for the security and welfare of its member states and citizens, it will have the power and the ability to improve Union law and directives to overcome barriers for EU citizenship and to reduce differences between member states. Furthermore, to create a Federal government, (EU) institutions and democracy have to be changed. For instance, the EU can develop and introduce facultative EU wide referenda on secondary legislation to improve the legitimacy of the EU. This can trigger a binding EU wide vote on certain decisions of secondary legislation that have been taken at the EU level. As a result, decisions at the EU level would be more in line with the preferences of a majority of citizens (Cheneval, 2016).

Secondly, civil society can play a role by fostering innovations. *“Civil society has the ability to experiment, move faster than government and act as an agent of change”* (World Economic Forum, 2013, p.14). For instance, civil society can develop and introduce working programmes to stimulate exchanges of youth and professionals to overcome differences between western and eastern countries. Such programmes can help to decrease brain drain from eastern to western countries, but civil society actors can also foster other innovations to decrease brain drain and to create solidarity for equality. This gives civil society actors an important role too in contributing to a sustainable federal EU scenario in which EU citizenship for all is safeguarded.

5.4 A ‘Marketized’ Europe – scenario 3: more Europeanism, more market

What will happen with EU citizenship?

With weak governments and society driven by multi-national corporations, EU citizenship in terms of economic, political, social and civil rights are under pressure. Citizens are primarily consumers and employees. Their access to rights, such as health care, education and training, social security and assistance, depends on their market or labour position. This makes citizens vulnerable and places large groups outside the system, as for example economically inactive citizens (Pennings et al., 2016; Van Eijk and Phoa, 2016). There is also an evident move towards a knowledge-based economy and attracting the ‘brightest and the best’ across the EU. This results in restricted access for lower skilled workers (Anderson et al., 2014), but also groups as youth and elderly (Knijn et al., 2014) are vulnerable. Furthermore, market actors like multi-national corporations gain power because they possess valuable (consumer) data. Some civil rights such as the right to data protection and the right to privacy, are under threat. However, rights that may contribute to the profit of the private corporations, such as the freedom of movement of workers and the freedom of goods and capital, will be promoted.

In this scenario, the values behind EU citizenship are only limited protected. Weak governments make ‘democracy and political participation’ questionable. Political participation in these representative democracies hardly touch the real market powers. ‘European unity in diversity’ is not regarded to be a value in itself in this scenario. To some extent there is European unity due the existence of the single market. And as a spillover effect of linguistic unification there is even more cultural unity than ever, but the value of cultural diversity is neglected.

The access to citizenship rights depends on the contribution to the economic welfare of the EU. Those who contribute have access to rights and are protected. Therefore ‘inclusiveness and solidarity’ and ‘protection and human security’ only exist for those who contribute to society. Groups that do not have only limited access to the labour market are vulnerable, such as lower skilled workers (Anderson et al., 2014), economically inactive EU citizens (Pennings et al., 2016; Van Eijk and Phoa, 2016), and youth and elderly (Knijn et al., 2014). This will lead to growing inequalities and has a negative effect on social cohesion in countries and on the level of the EU. Eventually this might lead to violent conflicts within the EU. In sum, Europeanism and a dominance of especially market actors affect EU citizenship. In this scenario, EU citizenship is likely to become more restricted and exclusive.

Repertoire of action

In this scenario, individual citizens and civil society can play an important role to foster EU citizenship and to express the importance of the values behind it. In case of only a minimal government protection, it is like that citizens will organise themselves. Citizens can make a change through claiming rights in social movements. Citizens as consumers and employees can put pressure on the market actors to safeguard citizens’ rights by, for instance, organising strikes or boycotting organisations (Kloosterboer, Van der Kolk and Runje, 2015). Secondly, civil society can play a critical role in moderating the impacts of the market. *“Where governments are weak, civil society can play a critical role as a catalyst, facilitator and convener between sectors – creating the political space for difficult policies to be designed, accepted and implemented”* (World Economic Forum, 2013, p.32).

5.5 A Europe of Patchwork Markets – scenario 4: more nationalism, more market

What will happen with EU citizenship?

In this scenario the former EU is driven by the market: only those rights that do not intervene with the functioning of the market exist. This implies that the focus is primarily on economic rights; such as the right to have a business and the freedom of goods, services and capital. However, EU economic rights only exist between countries who managed to agree in multi-lateral and bi-lateral agreements. Access to rights strongly depends on the contribution to the national economy and national economic welfare. This makes lower skilled workers (Andersson et al., 2014), economically inactive EU citizens (Pennings et al., 2016; Van Eijk & Phoa, 2016), and youth and elderly (Knijn et al., 2014) extremely vulnerable. Due to the strong focus on nationalism, also other groups are vulnerable in this scenario, such as EU migrant citizens (Seeleib-Kaiser and Chase, 2015), mobile EU citizens (De Waele, 2016) and asylum seekers (Anderson et al., 2015; 2016). Moreover, in a profit driven society like in this scenario, it is possible that health care, education and security are privatised. Access to these services is only available for those who can afford it. This leads towards growing social inequality and new divides between countries, regions and groups.

The values of EU citizenship are not guarded. There is a weak national government, which makes a mature ‘democracy’ as well as ‘political participation’ questionable. In case citizens do have political rights, the question is to what extent they will exercise their political rights due to a lack of trust in public authorities. In this scenario there is no ‘European unity in diversity’, no guaranteed ‘peace and stability’ and no ‘inclusiveness and solidarity’. ‘Protection and human security’ is only available for

citizens who can allow to pay for it and who have access to some rights based on their contribution to economic welfare.

In this scenario, nationalism is combined with strong markets. Markets strive for growth, they want to expand and globalize. This does not match with nationalism as a dominant forces. A first and ultimate consequence of this could be conflict and war. Competition between countries, large differences in economic prosperity and strong borders, can lead to extremism. An second and alternative outcome could be that eventually this scenario, after severe crisis, will turn a development in the direction of a global market and a more cosmopolitan world, comparable to the third scenario, but even beyond EU borders. The patchwork market is a highly unstable world in which there is no place for EU citizenship.

Repertoire of action

In this scenario, citizens and civil society can play an important role to foster EU citizenship and to give voice to claims for national citizenship. Citizens can counter market powers by creating a social movement. Citizens can organise strikes or boycott organisations. In this way, citizens as a consumer and employee can put pressure on the market (Kloosterboer, Van der Kolk and Runje, 2015). In line with that, citizens can organise themselves in trade union to claim rights. For instance, they can claim to have a role in trade agreements. Secondly, civil society can play a role in moderating the impacts of the market, for instance to have a role as catalyst, facilitator and convener between sectors. In this way, civil society can create the political space for difficult policies to be designed, accepted and implemented (World Economic Forum, 2013, p.32).

6. Conclusion

The aim of this scenario study is to stimulate the discussion on what repertoires of action by which actors in what circumstances might protect, foster or boost EU citizenship in different thinkable alternative futures. The results of the bEUcitizen project show that being an EU citizen does not guarantee inclusion: barriers towards EU citizenship exist and the chances and opportunities to exercise rights and participate in the community differ between countries, groups and in time.

We outlined four thinkable scenarios, some more utopian and some more dystopian in character. In all scenarios there is however room for manoeuvre, there is something to choose. Citizens can organise themselves when there is minimum government protection and citizens as a consumer and employee can put pressure on the market by, for instance, organising strikes or boycotting organisations (scenario 3 and 4). When national governments are strong (scenario 1 and 2), governments have the opportunity and resources to protect their own citizens and safeguard EU citizenship by, for instance, strengthening national law and legislation. Besides, in scenario 2, where we imagine a development towards a federal EU, the EU can improve Union law and directives to overcome barriers towards EU citizenship and reduce differences between member states.

A significant outcome of the analysis in research and during workshops is that in all scenarios civil society plays a critical role. Civil society can foster innovations in scenario 1 and 2 and can moderate the impacts of the market in scenario 3 and 4. This gives civil society actors a major role in safeguarding EU citizenship. Investing in a resilient civil society is regarded to be of high importance to protect, foster and develop EU citizenship.

Although a resilient civil society creates opportunities for safeguarding EU citizenship in the future, it calls for action today to contribute to positive developments. As quoted in the introduction of this report: *“Scenarios are stories about the future, but their purpose is to make better decisions in the present”* (Gerald Davis, executive Chair of the World Energy Scenarios flagship study). To contribute to a resilient civil society who can play a major role in safeguarding EU citizenship in the future, cross-sectoral relationships need to be developed (World Economic Forum, 2013, pp.33-34). This asks for time, actions and involvement of civil society actors, business- and government leaders from now on.

The World Economic Forum concluded in *‘The Future Role of Civil Society’* (2013) that the role of civil society will gain in importance in the future. In line with their conclusion, they discussed how to shape a resilient civil society. For our scenario study, this discussion is important too. If civil society is able to play potentially such an important role in safeguarding EU citizenship, the question is what should be done and by whom to make civil society more resilient. The World Economic Forum (2013, p.5) mentioned the importance of retaining civil society core missions and roles, integrity and high levels of trust. They also mentioned that this will not be enough for the future. In addition, civil society should work in a more cross-sectoral space. Civil society can no longer work in isolation and civil society actors should look into effective ways to face challenges. To do so, civil society needs to engage businesses and governments to *“effectively inspire, support and shape an innovative change agenda at all necessary global and local levels”* (World Economic Forum, 2013, p.33). To succeed civil society must first of all continue to hold all stakeholders, including itself, to the highest level of accountability. Secondly, civil society actors have to play an important role in the creation of a political and social space for cross-sectoral relationships (World Economic Forum, 2013, pp.33-34).

Next to civil society actors themselves, business- and government leaders play a role too in shaping a resilient civil society. Corporations can step up, embrace innovative approaches and collaborate with new networks and actors. Furthermore, government leaders can invest in capacity-building, promote long-term stability and build integrated consultation processes with civil society actors and businesses in developing policies (World Economic Forum, 2013, p.34). In this way, they contribute to community building and shaping a resilient civil society.

Furthermore, to prepare the next generation for thinkable futures and give them the opportunity to be able to act in these futures the development of high quality of (EU) citizenship education and civic education in all EU Member States is needed. Bakker et al. (2016) examined policies and practices of citizenship education in seven EU Member States. Although the research results show that citizenship policies and practices differ widely between the examined countries, all countries share a similar approach regarding to EU citizenship. The European dimensions of citizenship is a highly neglected area within the national curricula. When attention is paid to the European dimension, the focus is merely on the theoretical and factual knowledge on the EU and its institutions. However, more is needed to prepare the next generation to act and participate in thinkable future scenarios. EU citizenship education should focus on the promotion of values and the training of skills needed to exercise EU citizenship rights and the development of active, participating EU citizens who are able to act in the EU of the future.

References

Anderson, B., Shutes, I. and Walker, S. (2014). *D10.1 Report on the rights and obligations of citizens and non-citizens in selected countries*. Available from <http://beucitizen.eu/publications/report-on-the-rights-and-obligations-of-citizens-and-non-citizens-in-selected-countries/>

Anderson, B., Shutes, I. and Walker, S. (2015). *D10.2 The 'migrant' in data: report on analysis of national and European datasets on employment, inactivity and unemployment rates, and benefits uptake by specific groups*. Available from <http://beucitizen.eu/publications/report-on-analysis-of-european-datasets-on-employment-inactivity-and-unemployment-rates-d10-2/>

Anderson, B., Shutes, I., Walker, S., Gal, J., Alfasi-Hanley, M., Keidar, E., Murphy, K., Baričević, V., Lepianka, D. and Ramos Martin, N.E. (2016). *D10.3 Citizenship and Work: Case Studies of Differential Inclusion/Exclusion*. Available from <http://www.beucitizen.eu/>

Archick, K., Belkin, P., Blanchard, C.M., Humud, C.E., Mix, D.E. (2015). *European Fighters in Syria and Iraq: Assessments, Responses, and Issues for the United States*. Congressional Research Service. Available from <https://www.fas.org/sgp/crs/row/R44003.pdf>

Bakker, W.E., De Krijger, F., Koska, V., Puetter, U. (2016). *D11.1 Assessing policy implications for EU citizenship. Exploring options for an impact assessment framework*. Available from <http://beucitizen.eu/publications/working-paper-on-assessing-policy-implications-for-eu-citizenship-deliverable-11-1/>

Bakker, W.E. and Van der Kolk, M. (2016). *D11.2 Towards Impact Assessment Indicators for EU citizenship*. Available from: <http://www.beucitizen.eu>

Bakker, W.E., Van der Kolk, M. Berkely, D. and Koska, V. (2016). *D8.10 The quest for a European civic culture. The EU and EU citizenship in policies and practices of citizenship education in seven EU member states*. Soon available from <http://www.beucitizen.eu>

Cheneval, F. (2016). *European policy brief: towards a more legitimate form of direct democracy in the European Union*. Available from <http://beucitizen.eu/publications/european-policy-brief-towards-a-more-legitimate-form-of-direct-democracy-in-the-european-union/>

Conversi, D. (2010). Cultural Homogenization, Ethnic Cleansing, and Genocide. In *The International Studies Encyclopedia* (pp.719-742). Wiley-Blackwell. Available from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Daniele_Conversi/publication/231537076_Cultural_Homogenization_Ethnic_Cleansing_and_Genocide/links/09e41506b746ad5123000000.pdf

De Waele, H. (2016). *D7.6 Access to travel documents*. Available from <http://beucitizen.eu/>

Dell'Olio, F. (2005). *The Europeanization of citizenship – Between the ideology of Nationality, Immigration and European identity*. Hants: Ashgate Publishing Limited.

Eberl, O. and Seubert, S. (2016). *European policy brief: European political citizenship 2030: post-democracy with populist activism or an integrated political and social citizenship?* Available from <http://beucitizen.eu/publications/european-policy-brief-european-political-citizenship-2030-postdemocracy-with-populist-activism-or-an-integrated-political-and-social-citizenship/>

European Commission (2017). *White paper on the Future of Europe: reflections and scenarios for the EU2027 by 2025*. Belgium: Brussels. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/white_paper_on_the_future_of_europe_en.pdf

European Parliament (2016). *Recent migration flows to the EU*. Available from: [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/ReqData/etudes/ATAG/2016/580893/EPRS_ATA\(2016\)580893_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/ReqData/etudes/ATAG/2016/580893/EPRS_ATA(2016)580893_EN.pdf)

European Youth Press (2016). *Shaping Europe: 50 ideas for a better future. The EYE report 2016*. Luxembourg: Strassbourg.

Gaus, D. and Seubert, S. (2016). *D8.6 Report on voter turnout for the European Parliament and Political Equality in the EU*. Available from <http://www.beucitizen.eu/>

Goerens, C. (2016). *EU citizenship*. Available from <https://www.charlesgoerens.eu/blog-charles/eu-citizenship/> (23th of February, 2017).

Granger, M. (2016). *European policy brief: revisiting the foundation of European Union citizenship: making it relevant to all European Union citizens*. Available from <http://beucitizen.eu/publications/european-policy-brief-revisiting-the-foundation-of-european-union-citizenship-making-it-relevant-to-all-european-union-citizens/>

Institute for Economics and Peace (2015). *Global Terrorism Index 2015: measuring and understanding the impact of terrorism*. Available from <http://economicsandpeace.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/Global-Terrorism-Index-2015.pdf>

Kloosterboer, M., Van der Kolk, M., Runje, L. (2015). *Breaking Down Barriers: Future scenarios on youth and citizenship in 2030*. Available from http://beucitizen.eu/wp-content/uploads/Report_Breaking_down_barriers_for_youth-1.pdf

Knijn, T., Yerkes, M. and Šipic, J. (2014). *D9.1 A Report on the transposition of EU guidelines and directives in the most recent 27 National Reform Programme*. Available from http://beucitizen.eu/wp-content/uploads/Deliverable-9.1_report-NRPs.pdf

Kymlicka, W. & Noman, W. (1995). *Return of the Citizen: A Survey of Recent Work on Citizenship Theory*. In R. Beiner (Eds.), *Theorizing Citizenship* (pp.?). Albany: State University of New York Press.

Leydet, D. (2011). *Citizenship*. *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. <http://plato.stanford.edu/entries/citizenship>

Luppi, M., Oomkens, R., Knijn, T. and Weicht, B. (2015). *D9.6 Citizenship in the context of migrant care work: regimes, rights & recognition*. Available from http://beucitizen.eu/wpcontent/uploads/Deliverable_9.6_final1.pdf

Marshall, T.H. (1950). *Citizenship and social class – and other essays*. London/New York: Cambridge University Press.

Meinert, S. (2014). *Field Manual – Scenarios building*. European Trade Union Institute. Belgium: Brussels.

NASA (2016). *Global Climate Change: vital signs of the planet*. Available from <http://climate.nasa.gov/evidence/> (15th of July, 2016).

Nelson, T.D. (2009). *Handbook of prejudice, stereotyping, and discrimination*. New York: Psychology Press – Taylor & Francis Group.

Pennings, F. et al. (2016). *D6.2 EU Citizenship and Social Rights, a Comparative Report*. Available from <http://beucitizen.eu/wp-content/uploads/D6.2-Report-on-the-transposition-of-the-relevant-EU-instruments-in-the-Member-States.pdf>

Pew Research Center (2014). *AI, Robotics, and the Future of Jobs*. Available from <file:///C:/Users/3467147/AppData/Local/Google/Chrome/Downloads/Future-of-AI-Robotics-and-Jobs.pdf>

Rolandsen Agustín, L. and Nissen, A. (2015). *D9.5 Positions and opinions of political groups in the European Parliament and European social movements on civil, political and social rights for women, migrants and minorities*. Available from http://beucitizen.eu/wp-content/uploads/Deliverable-9.5_final1.pdf

Scearce, D., Fulton, K. (2004). *What If? The art of scenario thinking for non profits*. Emeryville, Global Business Network.

Seeleib-Kaiser, M. (2017). *European policy brief: limited social rights and the case for a European Minimum Income Scheme*. Available from <http://beucitizen.eu/publications/european-policy-brief-limited-social-rights-and-the-case-for-a-european-minimum-income-scheme/>

Seeleib-Kaiser, M. and Chase, E. (2015). *D6.1 Research paper on categorization of social welfare benefits with respect to the factors hindering access by other EU nationals and third country nationals*. Available from <http://beucitizen.eu/publications/social-rights-of-eu-migrant-citizens-a-comparative-perspective>

Shell (2008). *Scenarios: An Explorer's Guide*. The Netherlands: The Hague.

Terazi, E. and Şenel, S. (2011). 'The Effects of the Global Financial Crisis on the Central and Eastern European Union Countries'. In: *International Journal of Business and Social Science* 2(17). Available from http://www.ijbssnet.com/journals/Vol_2_No_17/25.pdf

Van der Putten, F., Rood, J. and Meijnders, M. (2016). *Great Powers and Global Stability: Clingendael Monitor 2016*. Clingendael, Netherlands Institute for International Relations. Available from http://www.clingendael.nl/sites/default/files/clingendael_monitor2016-great_powers_and_global_stability-eng_0.pdf

Van Eijken, H. and Phoa, P. (2016). *D7.3 Exploring obstacles in exercising core EU citizenship rights*. Available from <http://www.beucitizen.eu>

Wilkinson, A. and Kupers, R. (2014). *The essence of scenarios. Learning from the Shell Experience*. Amsterdam, Amsterdam University Press.

World Economic Forum (2013). *The Future Role of Civil Society*. Switzerland: Geneva.